

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Project Management Guide

Deliverable 1.1

Work Package 1

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Executive summary

This document compose the Project Management Guide (PMG) of the eDNAqua-Plan, which is implemented under the framework of the European Commission (EC) Horizon Europe funding programme dedicated to research and innovation. The eDNAqua-Plan PMG serves as a reference document for all project members, notably outlining: i) the summary of the goals and objectives of the project; ii) the details of the project management and governance (organizational structure), roles and responsibilities of the participants; iii) the definition of the main communication channels; iv) the procedures and management tools implemented to ensure the successful completion of the project (i.e., schedule, reporting, financial guide, etc.). The guide is based on the terms and conditions agreed under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement to help all partners comply with the agreements.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EC	European Commission
ECB	European Central Bank
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAB	International Advisory Board
IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
LifeWatch-ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
PIC	Project Implementation Committee
PMG	Project Management Guide
PMT	Project Management Team
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise(s)
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Suomen Ympäristökeskus
UDE	Universität Duisburg-Essen
ULOD	Uniwersytet Łódźki
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de València
VAT	Value Added Tax
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee
WP	Work Package(s)
WU	Wageningen University

1. Purpose of the document

The Project Management Guide (PMG) of the Horizon Europe eDNAqua-Plan project provides a guide to be used by all eDNAqua-Plan members to ensure an understanding of their roles and responsibilities in delivering the project through efficient and well managed processes. This document should be used by partners to complement the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Further guidelines may also be found on the European Commission (EU) portal. The PMG:

- Summarizes the goals and objectives of the project;
- Details the project management and governance (organizational structure), roles and responsibilities of the participants;
- Describes the main communication channels;
- Highlights the procedures and management tools implemented to ensure the successful completion of the project (schedule, reporting, financial guide, quality control, risk management).
- Some aspects of the PMG will be developed in more details in other documents such as:
- The Data Management Plan (DMP);
- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP).

The PMD is an evolving document. The EMBRC-ERIC Project Management Team is in charge of:

- Producing the first PMG;
- Answering any questions/comments about the PMG;
- Updating the PMG during the project.

All eDNAqua-Plan members and affiliated partners have access to this document and are invited to give suggestions any time by contacting the eDNAqua-Plan Project Manager (claire.laguionie@embrc.eu with the email subject: request to update the PMG) explaining what changes/additions/deletions are required and why. If you want to share this document outside of the eDNAqua-Plan Consortium, please first contact the Coordinator: nicolas.pade@embrc.eu.

Note that this deliverable summarizes the terms and conditions stated in different contractual documents, to ensure compliance to what has been agreed upon. Whenever relevant, the source reference document is mentioned throughout the text. The reference documents of the project are:

- The Grant Agreement and its annexes;
- The Consortium Agreement;
- The Annotated Model Grant Agreement: aimed at assisting European Union (EU) grant beneficiaries;
- The Horizon Program Guide.

2. eDNAqua-Plan project overview

The project name is “eDNAqua-Plan” and is funded by the European Union’s programme “Horizon Europe” under the grant agreement No. 101112800 within the call “Actions for the implementation of the Mission Restore our ocean waters by 2030” ([HORIZON- HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-09](#)). The project started on September 1st 2023 and is meant to end on 31st August 2026, having a duration of 36 months.

The coordinating partner of the project is EMBRC-ERIC under the direction of Nicolas Pade (nicolas.pade@embrc.eu), Executive director of EMBRC-ERIC, and the Project Manager is Paulina Marcela Ramírez Quevedo (paulina.r.quevedo@embrc.eu). eDNAqua-Plan had an overall budget of 1,978,252.00€, of which all of it comes as EU contribution. More information about the project can be found in:

- Web page: <https://ednaquaplan.com/>
- Horizon Europe projects' page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112800>
- Contact: eDNAqua@embrc.eu
- Twitter: [@eDNAqua_plan](https://twitter.com/eDNAqua_plan)
- BlueSky : [@ednaquaplan.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/ednaquaplan.bsky.social)
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/ednaqua-plan>

eDNAqua-Plan aims to collect information on existing projects, initiatives and infrastructures for aquatic monitoring in the EU and associated countries while providing an overview of all national and international activities of standardization and interoperationalization of methods and data workflows. The project seeks to assess the relevance and feasibility of the creation of a digital ecosystem of eDNA repositories and an integrated and dynamic reference library of marine and freshwater species that is open-access and based on FAIR principles to support future aquatic biodiversity monitoring programmes and mapping initiatives.

eDNAqua-Plan counts partners with international reach in its consortium (e.g. IOC/UNESCO, EMODnet, ELIXIR/EBI and OBIS) and the UN Ocean Decade Programs (Marine Life 2030, OBON, ODIS, Ocean Practices for the Decade). Therefore, eDNAqua_Plan aims to connect implement international standards and engage with international initiative to ensure compatibility between European initiatives on eDNA reference libraries..

In synergy with concurrent projects, eDNAqua-Plan will develop a collection of information on existing projects, initiatives and infrastructures for aquatic monitoring in the EU and associated countries; the provision of an overview of all national and international activities of standardization and interoperationalization of methods and data workflows; and an assessment on the relevance and feasibility of the creation of a digital ecosystem of eDNA repositories and an integrated and dynamic reference library of marine and freshwater species that is open-access and based on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles to support future aquatic biodiversity monitoring programmes and mapping initiatives.

eDNAqua-Plan will lead to marine and freshwater biodiversity DNA data that will be relevant to existing frameworks, being interoperable and connected to global frameworks and help decision making of marine and freshwater stakeholders, such as in the topics of policies, industry, research and society, so actors can determine the health, predict and monitor changes in a certain ecosystem and proactively manage it and their biodiversity. Furthermore, eDNAqua-Plan had the potential to support major EU biodiversity directives and global initiatives.

3. eDNAqua-Plan management structure and governance

The organizational structure of the project is composed by the following Consortium Bodies:

- A Project Management Team (1 Coordinator, 1 Project Manager);
- A Project Implementation Committee (PIC);
- Five Work Packages (WP);
- One external International Advisory Board (IAB);
- One General Assembly (GA).

eDNAqua-Plan is composed of 18 partners from 11 countries listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of eDNAqua-Plan partners

N°	Short name	Legal name	Country
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1	BIOPOLIS	Associacao Biopolis	Portugal
2	EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	Germany
3	EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre European Research Infrastructure Consortium	France
4	EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw- En Visserijonderzoek	Belgium
5	IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados	Greece
6	INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement	France
7	Lifewatch ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research	Spain
8	NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning	Norway
9	SSBE	Seascape Belgium	Belgium
10	SU	Sorbonne Université	France
11	SYKE	Suomen Ymparistokeskus	Finland
12	UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen	Germany
13	ULOD	Uniwersytet Lodzki	Poland
14	UMINHO	Universidade do Minho	Portugal
15	UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization	France
16	UVEG	Universitat de Valencia	Spain
17	VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee	Belgium
18	WU	Wageningen University	Netherlands

A. Bodies of the organizational structure of the eDNAqua-Plan project

1. General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) is composed by one representative of each partner of the project and it is chaired by the designated coordinator, in this case EMBRC-ERIC. The responsibilities of the GA are to ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium, it also formulates proposals and takes decisions in accordance with procedures set out in the Consortium Agreement, such as:

- Specific issues occurring during the project life;
- Content, Finance and intellectual property rights:
 - Proposals for changes of Grant Agreement Annex 1 and 3;
 - Proposal for changes to the Consortium agreement;
 - Changes to the Consortium Plan;
 - Modifications;
 - Withdrawal of background in Attachment 1;
 - Addition to Attachment 3 or 4;
- Evolution of the Consortium:
 - Entry of a new Party;

- Withdrawal of a Party;
- Identification of a breach by a Party;
- Declaration of a defaulting Party;
- Remedies to be performed by a defaulting Party;
- Termination of a defaulting Party;
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator;
- Suspension of all or part of the project;
- Termination of the project and Consortium agreement);
- Appointment of the Project Implementation Committee (PIC)

The GA meets at least once a year and extraordinary meetings can be requested by the Project Implementation Committee (PIC) or by at least a third of the GA members. The agenda of these meetings is set by the eDNAqua-Plan Project Management Team (PMT) under the following agreements:

- The notice of a meeting is written and distributed no later than 45 calendar days for ordinary meetings and 15 days for an extraordinary meeting;
- The agenda is shared by the PMT at least 21 days before each meeting (10 for an extraordinary meeting);
- Other Consortium members can propose additional agenda items at least 14 days before the meeting (7 for an extraordinary meeting).

The minutes of a GA meeting are in charge of the PMT and the document shall be shared with the Consortium within maximum 20 working days from the date of the meeting. If no objections are received within 15 days, the minutes are considered accepted.

The minimum quorum for a GA meeting to happen is of at least 2/3 of the GA members, once achieved this presence the GA meeting can be validated. In the case that the quorum is not reached the Coordinator will convene another ordinary meeting within 15 days. If the quorum is not reached once more, the Coordinator will convene an extraordinary meeting under the framework of a decision-making power even if 2/3 of the GA members are not present.

The decision-making is based on the following rules:

- Most decisions are reached if voted by the majority (2/3);
- A Party can exercise its veto right if its work, time, costs, liabilities, intellectual property right or other legitimate interest are severely affected by a decision (please refer to the Consortium agreement for more details on this procedure).

There is a list of specific decisions requiring an unanimous vote:

- Entry of a new Party;
- Approval of the settlement in the conditions of a withdrawal;
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the project and the Consortium agreement;
- Proposal for amendments to the Consortium or Grant agreement;
- Changes to the Consortium budgets.

2. Project Implementation Committee (PIC)

The Project Implementation Committee (PIC) is composed by the Work Package (WP) co-leaders and any other representative of eDNAqua-Plan appointed by the GA. The PIC is represented by the project coordinator at the GA, which is responsible for chairing the PIC meetings.

The responsibilities of the PIC cover the supervision of the execution of the project and the implementation of the decisions made by the GA. The PIC reports to and is accountable to the GA. Furthermore, the PIC is supported by the International Advisory Board (IAB) and the Project Management Team (PMT) in its decision-making process and the execution of the project.

The tasks of the PIC include:

- Preparing the General Assembly meeting (e.g. agenda,...);
- Seeking consensus among the Parties;
- Being responsible for the execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly;
- Monitoring the effective and efficient implementation of the project (operational management);
- Collecting at least every 6 months information on the progress of the project, assessing its compliance with the Consortium Plan and if necessary proposing modification of the later to the General Assembly;
- Supporting the Coordinator in preparing meeting with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables;
- Preparing content and timing of press releases and joint communications.

The meeting frequency of the PIC is stated to be every two months and/or at the request of the Coordinator. The PMT is in charge of making the call and defining the agenda of such meetings. The meeting notice shall be no sooner than 14 days that the proposed date of a meeting. In case of an extraordinary meeting the notice shall be seven days before the date of the proposed meeting.

The agenda of a PIC meeting should be shared by the PMT at least 7 days before a stated meeting and approved by the PIC members (no objections or proposed changes to the content of the agenda is a form of approval).

The minutes of a PIC meeting are under the responsibility of the PMT, meaning that they shall write and share this document with the PIC members. The minutes should be shared at maximum two working days after the meeting with the Consortium. If no objection to the minutes is received within 15 days, the minutes are considered accepted.

Table 2. List of eDNAqua-Plan PIC members

N°	Name	Institute	Role	WP
1	Nicolas Pade	EMBRC	Coordinator	1
2	Paulina M. Ramírez Quevedo	EMBRC	Project Manager	1
3	Spiros Papakostas	IHU	Co-leader	2
4	Ioannis Kavakiotis	IHU	Co-leader	2
5	Michal Grabowski	ULOD	Co-leader	2
6	Guy Cochrane	EMBL	Co-leader	2
7	Peter Woollard	EMBL	Co-leader	3
8	Wars Appeltans	UNESCO	Co-leader	3
9	Sofie Derycke	EV ILVO	Co-leader	4
10	Florian Leese	UDE	Co-leader	4

11	Vicente Fernandez	SSBE	Co-leader	5
12	Oonagh McMeel	SSBE	Co-leader	5

3. Coordinator

The coordinator of eDNAqua-Plan is Nicolas Pade from EMBRC-ERIC (nicolas.pade@embrc.eu). The coordinator acts as the intermediary between eDNAqua-Plan partners and the European Commission (EC) and is responsible for the overall coordination of the project and its execution. Other responsibilities of the coordinator include:

- Monitoring that eDNAqua-Plan members comply with their obligations under the Grant and Consortium Agreements (ensuring all partners are aware of their roles and responsibilities and working towards common objectives);
- Facilitating effective communication and collaboration among partners, EC, IAB...;
- Keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available;
- Collecting, reviewing and submitting reports and deliverables (including financial statement and related certification) on time and ensuring they meet the required quality standards;
- Transmitting documents/information of the project to any other Parties concerned and supervising the development and implementation of the dissemination and exploitation strategy to maximize the project impact;
- Managing the finances (monitoring expenses, ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe funding rules, and managing any financial risks);
- Providing, upon request, official copies or originals of in its sole possession to the requiring Parties;
- Providing copies of the Grant Agreement and its Annex;
- Being responsible for the intellectual property management (proper protection and exploitation), project ethics and data protection;
- Assessing the progress of the project implementation via the PIC meetings and deliverable follow-up;
- Identifying potential risks and setting up mitigation plan to address them.

4. Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team (PMT) is composed by the coordinator and the project manager and supported by the secretariat office of EMBRC-ERIC (Table 3). The PMT is appointed by the eDNAqua-Plan coordinator and appointed by the PIC.

Table 3. Members of the eDNAqua-Plan Project Management Team (PMT)

Name	Role	Responsibilities
Nicolas Pade	Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General scope of project objectives Quality control • Intellectual property management Risk management • Ensuring compliance of the project • Maximize project impact • Internal Communication Project planning
Paulina M. Ramírez Quevedo	Project manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget management Consortium management Reporting • Coordination support • Communication support

Alexandra Vasic	Finance	• Financial support
Guillaume Duspara	Finance	• Financial support

The PMT assists and facilitates the work of the PIC and the Coordinator, ensures the execution of the GA decisions, and runs the day-to-day management of the Project. The main tasks of the PMT are:

- Project management: overall management to ensure that eDNAqua-Plan is delivered on time and within budget at the required quality standards;
- Planning: setting a detailed project plan with clear timelines, milestones and deliverables;
- Coordination of the Consortium: ensuring coordination and smooth communication with all the project partners, in particular making sure that they are aware of their roles and responsibilities;
- Consortium management: facilitating communication and collaboration with project partners, EC, IAB and other audience;
- Reporting: Ensuring that all project reports are submitted on time and comply with Horizon Europe reporting requirements;
- Identifying potential risks and developing plans to mitigate or address them;
- Ensuring that all project outputs and deliverables meet the required quality standards.

The PMT shall meet at least once every two months, the agenda shall be set by the coordinator and the project manager a week earlier of the set date of the meeting, other members can add items to the agenda up to two days before the meeting. The minutes of the meeting shall be written by the project manager and shared no later than two working days after the meeting took place with the PMT.

5. Work Package co-leaders

Each Work Package (WP) co-leaders (Table 2) have been elected by the Consortium during the Grant writing phase. Each WP co-leader pair is responsible for the planning, progress monitoring, quality management and successful completion of their WP and of interacting with other WP according to the work plan. They must:

- Keep their WP on track and report its status to the PMT;
- Relay actions transmitted by the Coordinator, and plan and monitor their execution;
- Support the Coordinator through day-to-day management;
- Supervise the work of their WP team, organize Work Package meeting, identify issues, risks and if necessary, propose revision of the WP plan;
- Ensure that tasks and deliverables meet the quality criteria and are done in time.

WP co-leaders shall participate in the PIC meetings and are responsible for organizing internal WP meetings whenever necessary but no less than every two months. The WP co-leaders are in charge of sending the agenda to their corresponding WP team and the PMT at least a week before each meeting, new items can be added to the agenda at least two days before a meeting. The minutes of a meeting are the responsibility of the WP co-leaders and they shall be shared with the WP members and the PMT no more than two working days after a meeting took place.

6. Operational and advisory bodies

A. International Advisory Board (IAB)

The International Advisory Board (IAB) is formed by six renowned experts from the related field of the project, such as, eDNA, data, policy and marine and freshwater ecosystems. The IAB members are

proposed by the GA and appointed by the PIC during the first GA. The coordinator ensures that a non-disclosure agreement is executed between all parties and each IAB member.

The responsibilities of the IAB are:

- Providing advice and external points of view to the PIC for the correct implementation of the project to maximize beneficial outcomes to society;
- Advising the Consortium on industrial, political and societal changes or concerns that may influence the project objectives, priorities, methodologies, and expected impacts;
- Proposing changes to the direction of the project in line with stakeholder/user priorities for maximizing the exploitation and benefits of the project for the biodiversity sector;
- Assisting and facilitating the decision made by the GA;
- Advising the Consortium on how best to exploit the most promising results (where and how to transfer them) and support and amplify the dissemination of the project results.

The IAB meet once a year, typically during the GA but the body does not have voting rights. The PMT is in charge of sending the agenda to IAB at least a week before each meeting, new items can be added to the agenda at least two days before a meeting. The minutes of a meeting are the responsibility of the PMT and they shall be shared with the IAB members no more than two working days after a meeting took place.

4. Project communication

The Project Management Guide (PMG) gives a summary of eDNAqua-Plan communication, overall the communication of the project can be done at three levels: i) European Commission (EC) – the granting agency; ii) Internal level (among the members of the GA, IAB and PIC); iii) External levels (scientific communication, public outreach, stakeholder engagement).

A. Communication with the European Commission

The coordinator and the project manager of eDNAqua-Plan are the interlocutors to the European Commission through the exchanges with the EC's project officer, Andreas Palialexis, with the aim to ensure that the EC's project officer is informed about the effective execution of the project, this contemplates the following:

- Submission of deliverables and reports;
- Achievement of milestones;
- General Assemblies;
- Dissemination;
- Issues related to the project implementation (i.e., delays in the deliverables; occurrence of risks and related mitigation actions of the project; financial issues, etc.).

Each member of eDNAqua-Plan that wishes to communicate information or questions to the EC must do so via the PMT (paulina.r.quevedo@embrc.eu) with the email subject: Information/question for the EC project officer. In particular, each eDNAqua-Plan member shall communicate about any information, fact, problem and/or delay that can potentially affect the implementation of the project. The PMT will pass the corresponding information and questions to the EC project officer and will get back to eDNAqua-Plan members as soon as it gets a reply.

Each partner abides to provide all information reasonably required by the General Assembly, the PIC or by the coordinator to carry out its tasks and to responsibly manage the access of its employees to the EU Funding & Tenders Portal.

B. Internal communications

Internal communications aim to keep each eDNAqua-Plan member fully informed about the status, progress, opportunities and issues of the different ongoing and upcoming activities of eDNAqua-Plan.

1. Email distribution groups

Emailing is the main channel for eDNAqua-Plan interpersonal communication. Different email addresses have been set up to ensure an effective communication within and between WP and partners (Table 4). Email distribution lists are maintained and regularly updated by the PMT but it is the responsibility of all eDNAqua-Plan members to let the project manager know about any change in the corresponding email list (new hires, leaving people, etc.). The changes shall be made by email directed to Paulina.r.quevedo@embrc.eu with the subject: Request change to email distribution groups.

Table 4. eDNAqua-Plan distribution groups and associated email addresses

Diffusion group	Email address
WP1	eDNA-WP1@embrc.eu
WP2	eDNA-WP2@embrc.eu
WP3	eDNA-WP3@embrc.eu
WP4	eDNA-WP4@embrc.eu
WP5	eDNA-WP5@embrc.eu
All eDNAqua-Plan members	eDNA@embrc.eu
PMT	eDNA-PMT@embrc.eu
PIC	eDNA-PIC@embrc.eu

eDNAqua-Plan communication abides to the provisions of the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#). Each eDNAqua-Plan members wanting to be part of the email distribution group must give their consent through the dedicated [form](#). Each WP co-leader pair can set its internal communication channel.

The details of who is in each email distribution group is in the Administration & Management folder of the [eDNAqua-Plan shared folder](#).

The PMT is in charge of circulating to all or some of the eDNAqua-Plan members the following:

- Documents related to meetings (doodle, calendar invitation, agenda, minutes);
- EC Reports;
- Deliverables;
- Any relevant information obtained from sources outside of the project (other Horizon Europe projects, EC, agencies and industries);
- Scientific publications;
- Dissemination activities.

Each eDNAqua-Plan member is in charge of sending to the PMT any documents or request that they wish to pass on to the Consortium, such as:

- Documents related to meetings (doodle, calendar invitation, agenda, minutes);
- Reports;
- Deliverables;
- Any relevant information obtained from sources outside of the project (other Horizon Europe projects, EC, agencies and industries);
- Scientific publications;
- Dissemination activities.

All information shall be also added to the eDNAqua-Plan shared drive. Concerning the communication within the WP, the WP co-Leaders are in charge of defining what should be exchanged by emails and to whom. Communication, documents and important data for the whole project (not just a particular WP) should be always sent to the project manager and copied into the eDNAqua-Plan shared drive.

2. Internal meetings

The project meetings include (but are not limited to) the GA meeting, the PIC meeting, the PMT meeting and the WP meetings.

Every year, the General Assembly assesses the progress of the project. The Assembly has the authority to make decisions on specific issues, review the work plan, oversee WP progress, and showcase new opportunities for eDNAqua-Plan. The agenda, records of presentations and minutes are the responsibility of the PMT.

The PIC meeting, happening at least every 2 months, invites the WP co-leaders to provide an update on each WP and talk about items relevant to the project. The agenda, records of presentations and minutes are the responsibility of the PMT.

The PMT meeting are held as often as necessary and at least every 2 months. The agenda, records of presentations and minutes are the responsibility of the PMT.

The WP meetings are organized and planned by the WP co-leaders with their WP members. They can be regular or not but it is recommended to hold them no less than every 2 months. During these meetings, WP co-Leaders should:

- Review the progress of the WP and risks;
- Give updates;
- Discuss results;
- Present achieved goals (milestones and deliverables);
- Propose potential adjustment of the work plan if needed
- Give objectives for the coming months.

The WP co-leaders should ensure that agendas, any presentations held during the meeting and minutes that should be shared with the PMT no less than 2 working days after the meeting and that should be placed in the eDNAqua-Plan shared drive.

Ad-hoc workshops can also take place during the implementation of the project; these workshops are organized by the WP according to the activities set in the Grant Agreement and on the available budget. Again, agendas, presentation records, and minutes have to be organized by the WP/Task leaders and all these documents must be sent to the PMT no less than 2 days after the meeting took place and placed into the eDNAqua-Plan shared drive. In case these workshops are milestones/deliverables please refer to the milestones and/or deliverables section below for communicating documents to the PMT.

For a meeting, several steps should be followed:

- If no time is set, a doodle pole should be done to find the best date for the meeting as early as possible;
- Once set, a calling notice should be sent to give details about the time, date, venue/online, participants, aims and objectives of the meeting, agenda;
- The notice period should be as early as possible (1 month in advance whenever possible);
- Agenda should always be included in the calling notice, shared with the PMT and a copy should be stored on eDNAqua-Plan shared drive;
- During a meeting, a chairperson must be designated as well as someone to take minutes;
- A signed attendance sheet must be filled in that will be used for the reporting that will be sent to the PMT after the meeting;
- After the meeting, minutes should be sent no less than 2 working days after the meeting for comments and approval with a given deadline. Once agreed, a copy of the minutes should be stored on eDNAqua-Plan shared drive and shared with the PMT.

3. Internal communication about issues

When an issue arises at a task level, a vertical communication is encouraged (Figure 1). Any issue that could lead to deviations to the work plans should be reported up to the Task Leader. If the deviation is expected to have an impact on the content or delivery of any deliverables or milestones within that WP or on a task within another WP, this should be reported by the WP co-leaders to the coordinator who can propose methods to manage the deviation and pass the proposal to the PIC members and if needed to the General Assembly for approval. If accepted by the General Assembly the proposed changes are passed to the EC Project Officer for the next stage of approval.

Figure 1. eDNAqua-Plan hierarchy from the General Assembly to the Task team

C. External communications

Dissemination is a key part of eDNAqua-Plan to ensure result sharing, the implementation of the outcomes of the project and that any future or on-going research builds upon it (rather than duplicating its works).

There are four main target groups for eDNAqua-Plan external communications:

- Industry;
- Scientific community;
- Policy community;
- Society.

All eDNAqua-Plan members are expected to give time for communication activities; in particular, each participant shall disseminate their results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public. One of the main tools for disseminating information about the project and its achievement is eDNAqua-Plan website as well as eDNAqua-Plan social media. All material that should be added to the eDNAqua-Plan website should be shared with the eDNAqua-Plan project manager.

In case of important press/media release, the EC should be warned beforehand to be able to advertise the release. eDNAqua-Plan members should give advance warning to the PMT so they have time to communicate with the EC Project Officer about it. A deadline of one month is recommended.

Regarding scientific publications, providing Open Access is mandatory for all Horizon Europe funded projects. Non-compliance can lead to a grant reduction and potential sanctions.

It is important to note that the funding EU logo shall be part of all eDNAqua-Plan external communication:

Figure 2. Funding European Union logo

D. eDNAqua-Plan data and document repository

To complete the framework of the eDNAqua-Plan data and document repository the Deliverable 1.3 of the eDNAqua-Plan project is in charge of presenting the Communication and dissemination plan.

A web-based shared eDNAqua-Plan drive has been set up which serves as a project tracking system accessible to all MBO members, in order that all information/documentation is easily accessible and kept up to date with little effort.

The eDNAqua-Plan shared drive is a Google Drive file storage and synchronization service which allows users to store files in the cloud, share files, and edit documents, spreadsheets, and presentations with collaborators. eDNAqua-Plan drive is shared among the persons recorded in the eDNAqua-Plan general mailing list. Requests for access to or change in access to the shared eDNAqua-Plan folder should be addressed to the Project Manager (paulina.r.quevedo@embrc.eu with the email subject: request to access/change eDNAqua-Plan shared drive).

The current structure of the eDNAqua-Plan shared drive is:

- Administration & Management;
 - Containing general information about eDNAqua-Plan, Kick-off meeting materials, deliverables and other relevant documents for the implementation of the management and administration of the project;
- Communication;
 - It consists of the logos that shall be used, templates, fact sheets and any communication piece produce under the framework of the project;

- IAB;
 - Contains all related files to the eDNAqua-Plan IAB, such as the agenda and minutes;
- PIC
 - Containing files related to the eDNAqua-Plan PIC, such as the agenda and minutes;
- WP
 - The folders inside are managed by the WP co-leaders and they are free to set up the folders inside as they seem more proper; nonetheless it is recommended to set the following folders:
 - Deliverables;
 - Task work and data (working space);
 - Scientific publication;
 - Dissemination;
 - Meetings.

Almost folders are meant to be updated by the PMT, with exception of the folders inside “WP” which responsibility is of the different co-leaders of each WP.

The eDNAqua-Plan shared drive has three main purposes:

- Being a repository for all documents and data generated during the project lifetime (documents must be uploaded under their correspondent folder and must be named in a clear way so that everybody can have an idea of what the file is about);
- Providing a common environment for the day-to-day work enabling several users to edit and upload files without overwriting them (working documents, drafts, templates);
- Ensuring that eDNAqua-Plan documents and data are backed up.

The eDNAqua-Plan shared drive will be copied to the PMT cloud system (Dropbox) system on the first of each month and on an external hard drive every 3 months to prevent the loss of data.

It is the responsibility of all eDNAqua-Plan members to store all eDNAqua-Plan data/documents on the eDNAqua-Plan shared drive.

5. Work plan and quality control

A. Work packages (WP)

The eDNAqua-Plan project is composed of five Work Packages (Table 5) and each of them is represented by two co-leaders.

Table 5. List of eDNAqua-Plan Work Packages and associated WP co-leaders

WP	WP title	Co-lead
1	Management, communication and stakeholder engagement	Nicolas Pade Paulina M. Ramírez Quevedo
2	Audit and gap analysis	Spiros Papakostas Ioannis Kavakiotis Michal Grabowski Guy Cochrane
3	Data standards, data linking and compatibility	Peter Woollard Ward Appeltans
4	Use cases: testing the developed eDNA library infrastructure	Sofie Dyrcke Florian Leese

Each WP is composed of tasks with a designated Task leader in charge of its completion, monitoring its progress, taking decision about the work distribution in their team, informing the WP co-leaders about the status of the task. The list of eDNAqua-Plan 14 tasks and associated Task Leaders is in Appendix 1 of this PMG. The Work Package tasks are tied to milestones and deliverables and the WP co-Leaders are responsible for organizing the practical work and ensuring the timely completion of these milestones and deliverables with the help of the PMT and Task leaders.

B. Work schedule

eDNAqua-Plan has started on the 1st September 2023 and will terminate on the 31st August 2026. The Kick-off meeting was held in Paris (at Sorbonne University, EMBRC-ERIC headquarters, Paris, France) the 3rd-4th October 2023. A Gantt chart for all the tasks of the project was defined in the Grant Agreement (Figure 3).

eDNAqua-Plan schedule is managed by different people at different levels:

- The PIC monitors the schedule status;
- The coordinator supervises the overall project schedule management;
- The WP co-leaders are in charge of their WP schedule management;
- The Task Leaders manage the detailed schedule of their task.

The schedule management of the project is a dynamic process throughout the project lifecycle. The schedule can be revised as more information becomes available. If schedule slippages are spotted, the PIC members should identify ways to get back on schedule.

In situations where a deliverable/milestone is expected to experience a delay that is not the Consortium's fault, it is imperative to inform the project manager (paulina.r.quevedo@embrc.eu) regarding the delay, its justification and the estimated time required to complete it with the email subject: Anticipated delay in milestones/deliverables. This will allow the coordinator to provide ample time to notify the EC project officer, who will then be able to implement the requisite adjustments within the EC portal to ensure the proper submission of the deliverable/milestone. Note that delays should not exceed a month time.

Figure 3. eDNAqua-Plan Gantt chart

C. Decision-making during the project

Different types of decisions are dealt with at different levels: i) Task; ii) WP; iii) Project; iv) Consortium.

Task level: Day-to-day scientific and management decisions of eDNAqua-Plan tasks are taken by the Task Leaders and if needed the WP co-Leaders.

WP level: Day-to-day scientific and management decisions of eDNAqua-Plan WPs are taken by the WP co-Leaders. Important decisions can be discussed at the PIC meeting if they may affect other parts of the eDNAqua-Plan project.

Project level: Day-to-day scientific and management decisions of the overall eDNAqua-Plan project are taken by the coordinator. The later can consult the PIC members and/or EC project officer if needed for advice or approval.

Consortium level: Major technical, operational, financial decisions as well as strategic decision and planning are taken by the General Assembly. The GA monitors eDNAqua-Plan using the work plan, anticipated risks and budgets. As detailed in section 3, decisions are mainly taken by a majority of 2/3rd of the votes. The GA decisions will be communicated in the minutes of their meeting and will be shared by email and placed into the shared Google Drive space of the project.

When conflicts arise within the Consortium regarding the carrying out of the project or other matters related to the project itself, they should be resolved by consent and as near the source as possible. If not possible, the conflict should be brought to the attention of the Coordinator who is in charge of proposing a solution (optimizing outcomes and maximizing benefits of all involved parties).

If the coordinator's attempt fails (or in case the conflict occurs at the Consortium level), the question will be brought to the first scheduled meeting of the PIC, or in case of urgency, an ad hoc meeting of the PIC

or GA called by the coordinator. The PIC and GA should propose procedure/measures to solve the conflict. If the conflict remains unsolved, the coordinator will notify the EC project officer. The participant may be declared not in line with the project execution and a contract termination can be asked.

D. EC reporting

There are two types of EC reporting: a continuous one and a periodic one; and English is the language for eDNAqua-Plan EC reporting. More details about the EC reporting are available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report-horizon-euratom-en.pdf>

1. Continuous reporting

The continuous reporting is collaborative, meaning that all beneficiaries can have edits. This type of reporting starts from the beginning of the project. The steps to follow are:

- Reception of a notification from the EC;
- Logging in to the Funding and Tenders Portal of the EC;
- Completion of that tabs available in the continuous reporting on the Funding and Tenders Portal of the EC.

The beneficiaries must continuously report on their progress (e.g. deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, critical risks, indicators, ...). The EC Portal publishes templates to be used for submission.

2. Periodic reporting

There will be three reporting periods for technical and financial aspects of eDNAqua-Plan:

- Reporting period 1 (M1-M18): date to report March-April 2024;
- Reporting period 2 (M19-M36): July-August 2025.

The technical report has two parts; the first one (part A) is composed on the following sections:

- Project summary;
- List of participants;
- List of deliverables;
- List of milestones (outputs/outcomes);
- List of critical risks;
- Dissemination and communication activities;
- Financial support to third parties.

The second part of the report (part B) is more descriptive and contains the following sections:

- Explanation of the work carried out and overview of the progress (objectives, explanation of the work carried out by WP, impact);
- Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s) (if applicable);
- Exploitation primarily in non-associated third countries (if applicable);
- Open science;
- Deviations from annex 1 and annex 2 (if applicable);
- A summary for publication by the EC.

The last periodic report is a final activity report divided in two parts:

- A final technical report with a summary for publication containing:

- An overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
- The conclusions on the action;
- The socio-economic impact of the action.
- A final financial report containing:
- A final summary financial statement, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance;
- A certificate on the financial statements for each beneficiary.

All beneficiaries must contribute to the periodic reporting which will be coordinated, put together, reviewed and submitted by eDNAqua-Plan PMT. The WP co-leaders are in charge of filling out their sections and the PMT will compile it. The same steps as for deliverable submission will apply for completing the periodic reports. The WP co-leaders should in particular give information to the PMT about:

- Technical progress of each task;
- Results obtained, deliverables completed, resources invested, compliance with the Gantt Chart;
- An overview of the budgetary situation based on the cost statements received from partners and payments made.

E. Deliverables

eDNAqua-Plan comprises 19 deliverables listed in Appendix 2 (sorted by due date). In case of delay, it is imperative to inform the PMT as soon as possible, explaining the reason for the delay, the remedial action plan and the new estimated time of completion. The submission of a deliverable has to follow several steps to ensure the quality management. The steps are detailed thereafter:

- Creation;
- Internal check;
- Approval by the Coordinator;
- Submission;
- Update;
- External check;
- Approval by the EC Project Officer;
- Publication.

Creation: authors must use the deliverable template given by eDNAqua-Plan Project Management Team (see Communication folder in the eDNAqua-Plan shared folder). Authors shall also agree with the deliverable leader on the authorship order.

Internal check: the steps of the internal check are managed by the PMT and consist in the alerts sent; the review of the submitted file; the feedback and the necessary modifications to the WP co-leaders. The Deliverable leader and the WP co-leaders shall receive the alerts from the PMT, in the first trimester, bimester and one month before the due date of the deliverable, to remind them of the corresponding deliverable deadline. The Deliverable leader will receive the feedback of the Deliverable submission two weeks before the deadline. Finally, the final Deliverable shall be sent to the PMT one week before the official deadline.

Approval: the approval of the Deliverable shall be made by the PMT and must be sent at least two days before the deadline of the Deliverable.

Submission: the PMT shall submit the Deliverable to the EU corresponding platform and send the confirmation message of submission to the Deliverable leader and the WP co-leaders. Also, a copy of the submitted Deliverable should be placed in the corresponding eDNAqua-Plan shared drive.

Update: if necessary, the Deliverable leader may request an update of the submitted deliverable. The PMT will manage the authorization with the EC project officer.

External check: the EC project office and/or external reviewers will assess the deliverable. If adjustments are required, the Deliverable leader will have five days to get back to the PMT for solving the required adjustments. The updated version considering the comments and revisions must be shared with the PMT at least three days prior to the deadline. Once submitted, the deliverable must be updated following the submission guidelines. The updated version will be placed in eDNAqua-Plan shared folder.

The Task leader is responsible for the scientific and technical quality of the Deliverable that is provided. Also, the WP co-leaders and the PMT are responsible for ensuring that standards and requirements are known and that the deliverable is produced on time and at the required quality standards.

The Deliverable structure is given by the deliverable template provided by the eDNAqua-Plan PMT and follow a set structure:

- Executive Summary – a brief summary of the key points of the main document;
- Table of Contents;
- Abbreviations and Acronyms;
- Introduction – an outline of the aims and objectives of the deliverable and where it fits in the context of the eDNAqua-Plan project. The introduction should also explain the interdependences related to this deliverable, whether this work is drawing on earlier tasks and deliverables and what other tasks will use this deliverable as input or for structuring their work;
- Main body of the report – this section will explain the task that was carried out and the results generated and illustrate the technical and scientific progress made within the task;
- Conclusions – this section should be a summary of the major outputs of the deliverable and the implications of the results on other parts of the project or the impact that the results will have for stakeholder groups;
- References;
- Annexes – Annexes of data or further information not suitable for the main body of the report either due to its detailed nature or separated for confidentiality purposes.

F. Milestones

eDNAqua-Plan comprises 11 milestones (Table 6). In case of delay, it is imperative to inform the PMT as soon as possible, explaining the reason for the delay, the remedial action plan and the new estimated time of completion. The milestone reporting follows the same submission steps as described for Deliverables in the past section, the steps are the following:

- Creation;
- Internal check;
- Approval by the Coordinator;
- Submission;
- Update;
- External check;
- Approval by the EC Project Officer;
- Publication.

Table 6. List of eDNAqua-Plan milestones with means of verification

No	Milestone name	WP	Means of verification	Due month
1	Consolidate stakeholder list of eDNA key actors important for the project, accompanied by a mapping of relevant projects and initiatives	1	List and mapping shared with the project consortium	18
2	Agreement on search criteria and system for inventorying	2	Written document shared with the project participants	2
3	Initial inventory analysis completed	2	Database shared with WP3	12
4	Gap analysis completed	2	Written document, summary published on website	12
5	Workshop for discussion on standards requirements	3	Proceedings published on website	13
6	Workshop for conceptualizing and writing on eDNA data ecosystem	3	Proceedings published on website	18
7	First version of the digital ecosystem landscape proposals prepared	3	Written proposal documents shared with WP4 and WP5	20
8	Operational input from all use cases to the inventories made in T2.1 and T2.2	4	Document shared with WP2	6
9	Operational input from all use cases on existing workflows and tools to be used in WP3	4	Document shared with WP3	14
10	Feedback on the digital ecosystem landscape v1	4	Document shared with WP3 and WP5	22
11	Sustainability plan draft v1 presented to the project Steering Committee	5	Document submitted to the management team	24

G. Risks

Eight risks were identified and assessed at the onset of the project and listed in Appendix 3. During the life of the project, new risks may be added to this list after discussion with the PMT and/or the PIC every six months. eDNAqua-Plan work plan and quality management allows monitoring the progress of the project and identify as soon as possible new risks as well as the relevance of the mitigation measures for dealing with anticipated risks.

The risk management and monitoring responsibility is shared at different levels:

- All eDNAqua-Plan members are responsible to communicate about anticipated risks and any other risks that may arise during the project to their WP co-Leaders and the PMT;
- WP co-Leaders are responsible to monitor the anticipated risks linked to their WP and assess the efficiency of the mitigation measure;
- The Coordinator and PMT are responsible for keeping track of the risks and evaluating the effectiveness of the response actions;
- In the case of new risk, both the Coordinator, PMT and involved WP co-Leaders are responsible to decrease their probability of occurrence and must find mitigation processes to reduce their severity.

6. Financial guide

The main objectives of the financial guide are to provide a quick reference and easy to follow guide to beneficiaries and to act as a reference document for external auditors, with the aim to ensure consistency in the financial management.

A. General principles

Grants are subject to the principles laid down in the Financial Regulation, in particular the principles of co-financing, prohibition of double financing and non-profit.

Co-financing principle: European Commission grants may not finance the entire cost of the action to be subsidized. The applicant must contribute to the implementation of the action either by way of own resources or by financial contribution from third parties (in the form of public or private assistance obtained elsewhere).

No double financing rule: Each action may give rise to the award of only one grant, there can be no duplicate European Commission funding of the same expenditure. The applicant must indicate the sources and amounts of any other funding received or applied for in the same financial year for the same action or for any other action and for routine activities (running costs).

No profit rule: The Community grant may not have the purpose or effect of producing a profit for the beneficiary. Profit is defined as a surplus of total actual receipts over the total actual costs of the action. Any income of the action must be indicated in the estimated budget and the final financial statement. The amount of the grant will be reduced by the amount of any surplus.

1. Definitions

Actual costs: Costs actually incurred, identifiable and verifiable, recorded in the accounts.

Annual workable hours: Annual workable hours is the period during which the personnel must be working at the employer's disposal and carrying out his/her activity or duties under the employment contract, applicable collective labor agreement or national working time legislation.

Associate partners: Other organizations may only participate in the action as associate organizations where this serves the aim of the action, on a no-cost basis. These organizations will not be a party of the grant agreement concluded with the Commission. Associated partners may not charge costs or contributions to the action and the costs of their tasks are not eligible.

Beneficiaries: Beneficiaries refer to the legal entities which have signed the Grant Agreement or the Accession Form and include the Coordinator.

Coordinator: Coordinator is the beneficiary that is the central contact point for the project and represents the European Commission's project adviser. In this project, the Coordinator is the beneficiary EMBRC-ERIC.

Direct costs: Direct costs are the costs of a project that can be clearly identified and specifically related to a particular grant, as set out in the Grant Agreement.

Estimated budget: It is the estimated eligible costs and the forms of costs, broken down by beneficiary and budget category.

Indirect costs: Indirect costs are calculated by applying the 25% flat-rate to the eligible actual costs or unit costs after the deduction of eligible subcontracting costs. The formula for calculating indirect costs is: $(\text{total eligible costs} - \text{subcontracting costs}) \times 25\%$.

Reporting period: Each project is divided into reporting periods. The length and number of the reporting periods is set out in the Article 21 and 22 of the Grant Agreement. The financial reports must be drawn up using the forms and template provided in Annex of the Financial Guideline.

Subcontractors: Subcontractors are external private organizations that can participate in the action if necessary for the implementation via an amendment in the Grant Agreement. The costs of subcontracted tasks (price charged by the subcontractor) are eligible and can be invoiced by the beneficiaries. The costs will be included in Annex 2 as part of the beneficiaries' costs (see Grant Agreement).

Third parties: Third parties are other entities outside beneficiaries, affiliated entities and associate organizations are considered as third parties.

B. Grant

The grant is an action grant which takes the form of a budget-based mixed actual cost grant (i.e. a grant based on actual costs incurred, but which may also include other forms of funding, such as unit costs or contributions, flat-rate costs or contributions, lump sum costs or contributions or financing not linked to costs).

The maximum grant amount is set out in the Data Sheet and in the estimated budget (Annex 2, Grant Agreement).

The funding rate for costs is 100% of the action's eligible costs.

The estimated budget for the action is set out in Annex 2. It contains the estimated eligible costs and contributions for the action, broken down by participant and budget category. The Grant Agreement Annex 2 also shows the types of costs and contributions (forms of funding) to be used for each budget category. If unit costs or contributions are used, the details on the calculation will be explained in Annex 2a.

Budget flexibility: The budget breakdown may be adjusted — without an amendment (see Article 39, Grant Agreement) — by transfers (between participants and budget categories), as long as this does not imply any substantive or important change to the description of the action in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement.

However:

- Changes to the budget category for volunteers (if used) always require an amendment;
- Changes to budget categories with lump sums costs or contributions (if used; including financing not linked to costs) always require an amendment;
- Changes to budget categories with higher funding rates or budget ceilings (if used) always require an amendment;
- Addition of amounts for subcontracts not provided for in Annex 1 either require an amendment or simplified approval in accordance with Article 6.2 of the Grant Agreement;
- Other changes require an amendment or simplified approval, if specifically provided for in Article 6.2 of the Grant Agreement.

C. Grant amendments

Concept of Grant amendments: The Grant Agreement specific data and options can be added, removed or changed via an amendment. If there are any changes to its terms & conditions (e.g. data or options specific to that agreement) and its annexes.

Amended provisions become an integral part of the agreement.

1. Changes requiring amendments

In terms of finance, amendments are necessary in three cases:

- Changes involving beneficiaries & linked third parties:
 - Addition of a new beneficiary;
 - Deletion of a beneficiary whose participation has been terminated because:
 - It has not signed the grant agreement;
 - It has not provided a declaration on joint & several liability as requested;
 - For some other reason;
 - Change of beneficiary;
 - Deletion or addition of linked third party;
 - Specific case: if a beneficiary's participation is terminated at the initiative of other beneficiaries.
- Change involving the Coordinator/principal beneficiary:
 - Change of Coordinator;
 - Change in the bank account the Coordinator uses for payments;
 - Change in the 'authorization to administer' option.
- Changes involving the financial aspects of the grant:
 - Change to Annex 2 or 2a of the Grant Agreement;
 - Change in the maximum grant amount, reimbursement rate(s), the estimated eligible costs of the project (if applicable, for example it is not applicable to lump sum pilot projects), the amount of pre-financing or the contribution to the Guarantee Fund;
 - Change concerning specific cost categories ('specific unit costs').

2. Changes not requiring amendments

Amendments are NOT necessary:

- For certain budget transfers;
- If the name or address of a beneficiary, linked third party or coordinator changes;
- If a universal takeover results in a change of beneficiary;
- If there is a change in the name of the bank or the address of the branch where the coordinator has an account, or in the name of the account holder.

3. Amendment procedure

Amendments may be requested by any of the parties. The Coordinator submits requests for amendment on behalf of the beneficiaries. The amendment request must include the reasons for the amendment and the appropriate supporting documents.

After the amendment is made, all amended provisions become an integral part of the Grant Agreement and all other provisions remain unchanged and continue to have full effect.

D. Eligible and ineligible costs and contributions

1. General eligibility conditions

The actual costs eligibility must:

- Be actually incurred by the beneficiary;
- Be incurred in the period set out in Article 4 of the Grant Agreement (with the exception of costs relating to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be incurred afterwards; see Article 21, Grant Agreement);

- Be declared under one of the budget categories set out in Article 6.2 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement;
- Be incurred in connection with the action as described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and necessary for its implementation;
- Be identifiable and verifiable, in particular recorded in the beneficiary's
- accounts in accordance with the accounting standards applicable in the country where the beneficiary is established and with the beneficiary's usual cost accounting practices;
- Comply with the applicable national law on taxes, labor and social security;
- Be reasonable, justified and must comply with the principle of sound financial management, in particular regarding economy and efficiency.

Unit costs or contributions (if any) eligibility:

- They must be declared under one of the budget categories set out in Article 6.2 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement;
- The units must:
 - Be actually used or produced by the beneficiary in the period set out in Article 4 (with the exception of units relating to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be used or produced afterwards; see Article 21, Grant Agreement);
 - Be necessary for the implementation of the action;
- The number of units must be identifiable and verifiable, in particular supported by records and documentation (see Article 20, Grant Agreement).

Flat-rate costs or contributions (if any) eligibility:

- They must be declared under one of the budget categories set out in Article 6.2 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement;
- The costs or contributions to which the flat-rate is applied must:
 - Be eligible;
 - Relate to the period set out in Article 4 (with the exception of costs or contributions relating to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be incurred afterwards; see Article 21, Grant Agreement).

Lump sum costs or contributions (if any) eligibility:

- They must be declared under one of the budget categories set out in Article 6.2 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement;
- The work must be properly implemented by the beneficiary in accordance with Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement;
- The deliverables/outputs must be achieved in the period set out in Article 4 (with the exception of deliverables/outputs relating to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be achieved afterwards; see Article 21).

Unit, flat-rate or lump sum costs or contributions according to usual cost accounting practices (if any) eligibility:

- They must fulfil the general eligibility conditions for the type of cost concerned;
- The cost accounting practices must be applied in a consistent manner, based on objective criteria, regardless of the source of funding.

Financing not linked to costs (if any) eligibility: the results must be achieved or the conditions must be fulfilled as described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement.

In addition, for direct cost categories (e.g. personnel, travel & subsistence, subcontracting and other direct costs) only costs that are directly linked to the action implementation and can therefore be attributed to it directly are eligible. They must not include any indirect costs (i.e. costs that are only indirectly linked to the action, e.g. via cost drivers).

In-kind contributions provided by third parties free of charge may be declared as eligible direct costs by the beneficiaries which use them (under the same conditions as if they were their own, provided that they concern only direct costs and that the third parties and their in-kind contributions are set out in Annex 1 (or approved ex post in the periodic report, if their use does not entail changes to the Agreement which would call into question the decision awarding the grant or breach the principle of equal treatment of applicants; 'simplified approval procedure').

2. Budget categories and form of costs

The budget categories and form of costs are in Table 7.

Table 7. eDNAqua-Plan budget categories and form of costs

Budget category	Forms of costs
Direct personnel costs	Actual costs / Unit costs
Subcontracting	Actual costs
Travel	Actual costs
Equipment	Actual costs
Other goods and services	Actual costs
Research infrastructure	Actual costs
Financial support to third parties	Actual costs
Indirect costs	Flat-rate costs

3. Eligibility condition for direct personal costs

Costs for employees (or equivalent) are eligible as personnel costs if they fulfil the general eligibility conditions and are related to personnel working for the beneficiary under an employment contract (or equivalent appointing act) and assigned to the action.

They must be limited to salaries (including net payments during parental leave), social security contributions, taxes and other costs linked to the remuneration, if they arise from national law or the employment contract (or equivalent appointing act) and be calculated on the basis of the costs actually incurred, in accordance with the following method:

- {Daily rate for the person multiplied by number of day-equivalents worked on the action (rounded up or down to the nearest half-day)}.

The daily rate must be calculated as:

- {Annual personnel costs for the person divided by 215}.

The number of day-equivalents declared for a person must be identifiable and verifiable (see Article 20, Grant Agreement). The actual time spent on parental leave by a person assigned to the action may be deducted from the 215 days indicated in the above formula. The total number of day-equivalents declared in EU grants, for a person for a year, cannot be higher than 215, minus time spent on parental leave (if any).

For personnel which receives supplementary payments for work in projects (project-based remuneration), the personnel costs must be calculated at a rate which:

- Corresponds to the actual remuneration costs paid by the beneficiary for the time worked by the person in the action over the reporting period;
- Does not exceed the remuneration costs paid by the beneficiary for work in similar projects funded by national schemes ('national projects reference');
- Is defined based on objective criteria allowing to determine the amount to which the person is entitled;
- Reflects the usual practice of the beneficiary to pay consistently bonuses or supplementary payments for work in projects funded by national schemes.

The national projects reference is the remuneration defined in national law, collective labor agreement or written internal rules of the beneficiary applicable to work in projects funded by national schemes. If there is no such national law, collective labor agreement or written internal rules or if the project based remuneration is not based on objective criteria, the national project reference will be the average remuneration of the person in the last full calendar year covered by the reporting period, excluding remuneration paid for work in EU actions.

If the beneficiary uses average personnel costs (unit cost according to usual cost accounting practices), the personnel costs must fulfil the general eligibility conditions for such unit costs and the daily rate must be calculated:

- Using the actual personnel costs recorded in the beneficiary's accounts and excluding any costs which are ineligible or already included in other budget categories; the actual personnel costs may be adjusted on the basis of budgeted or estimated elements, if they are relevant for calculating the personnel costs, reasonable and correspond to objective and verifiable information;
- According to usual cost accounting practices which are applied in a consistent manner, based on objective criteria, regardless of the source of funding.

Costs for natural persons working under a direct contract/Costs of personnel seconded by a third party against payment are also eligible as personnel costs, if they are assigned to the action, fulfil the general eligibility conditions and:

- Work under conditions similar to those of an employee (in particular regarding the way the work is organized, the tasks that are performed and the premises where they are performed);
- The result of the work belongs to the beneficiary (unless agreed otherwise).

They must be calculated on the basis of a rate which corresponds to the costs actually incurred for the direct contract or secondment and must not be significantly different from those for personnel performing similar tasks under an employment contract with the beneficiary.

Costs for SME owners and natural persons beneficiaries: The work of SME owners for the action (i.e. owners of beneficiaries that are small and medium sized enterprises not receiving a salary) or natural person beneficiaries (i.e. beneficiaries that are natural persons not receiving a salary) may be declared as personnel costs, if they fulfil the general eligibility conditions and are calculated as unit costs in accordance with the method set out in Annex 2a of the Grant Agreement.

4. Eligibility condition for direct subcontracting costs

Subcontracting costs for the action (including related duties, taxes and charges, such as non-deductible or non-refundable value added tax (VAT)) are eligible, if they are calculated on the basis of the costs actually incurred, fulfil the general eligibility conditions and are awarded using the beneficiary's usual

purchasing practices — provided these ensure subcontracts with best value for money (or if appropriate the lowest price) and that there is no conflict of interests (see Article 12, Grant Agreement).

Beneficiaries that are ‘contracting authorities/entities’ within the meaning of the EU Directives on public procurement must also comply with the applicable national law on public procurement.

Subcontracting may cover only a limited part of the action.

The tasks to be subcontracted and the estimated cost for each subcontract must be set out in Annex 1 and the total estimated costs of subcontracting per beneficiary must be set out in Annex 2 (or may be approved ex post in the periodic report, if the use of subcontracting does not entail changes to the Agreement which would call into question the decision awarding the grant or breach the principle of equal treatment of applicants; ‘simplified approval procedure’).

5. Eligibility condition for direct purchase costs

Purchase costs for the action (including related duties, taxes and charges, such as non- deductible or non-refundable value added tax (VAT)) are eligible if they fulfil the general eligibility conditions and are bought using the beneficiary’s usual purchasing practices — provided these ensure purchases with best value for money (or if appropriate the lowest price) and that there is no conflict of interests (see Article 12).

Beneficiaries that are ‘contracting authorities/entities’ within the meaning of the EU Directives on public procurement must also comply with the applicable national law on public procurement.

Travel and subsistence costs: Purchases for travel, accommodation and subsistence must be calculated as follows:

- Travel: on the basis of the costs actually incurred and in line with the beneficiary’s usual practices on travel;
- Accommodation: on the basis of the costs actually incurred and in line with the beneficiary’s usual practices on travel;
- Subsistence: on the basis of the costs actually incurred and in line with the beneficiary’s usual practices on travel.

Equipment costs: Purchases of equipment, infrastructure or other assets used for the action must be declared as depreciation costs, calculated on the basis of the costs actually incurred and written off in accordance with international accounting standards and the beneficiary’s usual accounting practices.

Only the portion of the costs that corresponds to the rate of actual use for the action during the action duration can be taken into account.

Costs for renting or leasing equipment, infrastructure or other assets are also eligible, if they do not exceed the depreciation costs of similar equipment, infrastructure or assets and do not include any financing fees.

Costs of other goods, works and services: Purchases of other goods, works and services must be calculated on the basis of the costs actually incurred. Such goods, works and services include, for instance, consumables and supplies, promotion, dissemination, protection of results, translations, publications, certificates and financial guarantees, if required under the Agreement.

6. Eligibility condition for other direct cost categories

- Costs for internally invoiced goods and services directly used for the action may be declared as unit cost according to usual cost accounting practices, if and as declared eligible in the call conditions, if they fulfil the general eligibility conditions for such unit costs and the amount per unit is calculated:
- Using the actual costs for the good or service recorded in the beneficiary's accounts, attributed either by direct measurement or on the basis of cost drivers, and excluding any cost which are ineligible or already included in other budget categories; the actual costs may be adjusted on the basis of budgeted or estimated elements, if they are relevant for calculating the costs, reasonable and correspond to objective and verifiable information;
- According to usual cost accounting practices which are applied in a consistent manner, based on objective criteria, regardless of the source of funding.

Note that 'Internally invoiced goods and services' means goods or services which are provided within the beneficiary's organization directly for the action and which the beneficiary values on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices. This cost will not be taken into account for the indirect cost flat-rate.

7. Eligibility condition for indirect costs

Indirect costs will be reimbursed at the flat-rate of 25% of the eligible direct costs (categories A-D, except volunteers' costs, subcontracting costs, financial support to third parties and exempted specific cost categories, if any).

8. Ineligible costs

The cost or contribution detailed below are ineligible.

Costs or contributions that do not comply with the conditions set out above (Article 6.1 and 6.2, Grant Agreement), in particular:

- Costs related to return on capital and dividends paid by a beneficiary;
- Debt and debt service charges;
- Provisions for future losses or debts;
- Interest owed;
- Currency exchange losses;
- Bank costs charged by the beneficiary's bank for transfers from the granting authority;
- Excessive or reckless expenditure;
- Deductible or refundable VAT (including VAT paid by public bodies acting as public authority);
- Costs incurred or contributions for activities implemented during grant agreement;
- Suspension (see Article 31, Grant Agreement).

Costs or contributions declared under other EU grants (or grants awarded by an EU Member State, non-EU country or other body implementing the EU budget), except for the following case:

- If the action grant is combined with an operating grant¹¹ running during the same period and the beneficiary can demonstrate that the operating grant does not cover any (direct or indirect) costs of the action grant.

Costs or contributions for staff of a national (or regional/local) administration, for activities that are part of the administration's normal activities (i.e. not undertaken only because of the grant).

Costs or contributions (especially travel and subsistence) for staff or representatives of EU institutions, bodies or agencies.

Others: Costs or contributions declared specifically ineligible in the call conditions.

E. European Commission financial reporting

The periodic financial report shall include :

- An individual financial statement from each beneficiary and from each linked third party, for the reporting period concerned;
- Details of the eligible costs for each budget category;
- A declaration of costs in the financial report by beneficiaries and linked third parties. Each beneficiary and each linked third party must declare that: the information provided is full, reliable and true; the costs declared are eligible; the costs can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations; and for the last reporting period that all the receipts have been declared. Amounts which are not declared in the individual financial statement will not be taken into account by EMBRC-ERIC;
- An explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary and from each linked third party, for the reporting period concerned;
- A periodic summary financial statement, consolidating the individual financial statements for the reporting period concerned and including - except for the last reporting period - the request for interim payment;
- If an individual financial statement is not submitted for a reporting period, it may be included in the periodic financial report for the next reporting period.

In addition, the beneficiaries must provide reports to request payments, in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 4.2):

- For additional prefinancing (if any): an additional prefinancing report;
- For interim payments (if any) and the final payment: a periodic report.

Revised financial statements sent after submitting a first version to EMBRC-ERIC will not be accepted – unless requested otherwise by EMBRC-ERIC. Each financial statement submitted to EMBRC-ERIC must show the same cost results as the documents which will be submitted to the auditor.

If some of the actual costs need to be corrected, it is only possible to do so in subsequent financial statements. If an incorrect amount was entered in a previous financial statement, that amount must be booked and marked as a complete cancellation in the next financial statement.

If necessary, actual costs that have not been submitted yet and that relate to previous periods can be entered in the current financial statement.

Audit findings and findings made by EMBRC-ERIC will be considered by EMBRC-ERIC and communicated to the Recipient. The implementation of these findings shall be handled separately from the regular financial statements. The Recipient shall not make additional adjustments in the subsequent financial statements in this regard.

The final cumulative total calculated for all financial statements must not exceed the total amount in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement.

The financial statements must be drafted in euro. Beneficiaries with general accounts established in a currency other than the euro must convert the costs recorded in their accounts into euro, at the average

of the daily exchange rates published in the C series of the Official Journal of the European Union (ECB website), calculated over the corresponding reporting period. If no daily euro exchange rate is published in the Official Journal for the currency in question, they must be converted at the average of the monthly accounting exchange rates published on the European Commission website (InforEuro), calculated over the corresponding reporting period.

Beneficiaries with general accounts in euro must convert costs incurred in another currency into euro according to their usual accounting practices.

The beneficiary bears all risks associated with foreign currency fluctuations between the Euro and the local currency and also between the local currency/Euro and the currency or currencies of project expenditure.

Consequences of non-compliance: If a report submitted does not comply with this Article, the granting authority may suspend the payment deadline (see Article 29, Grant Agreement) and apply other measures described in Chapter 5, Grant Agreement.

If the Coordinator breaches its reporting obligations, the granting authority may terminate the grant or the Coordinator's participation (see Article 32, Grant Agreement) or apply other measures described in Chapter 5, Grant Agreement.

F. Payment and recovery

Beneficiary financial identification: Each Beneficiary must fill the Financial Identification (see Annex 1 of the Financial Identification) signed and dated by its director and its bank. The Financial Identification must be sent to the project's Coordinator. Payment shall be made to the beneficiary's bank account in Euro by EMBRC-ERIC acting as Coordinator).

Payment procedure: Payments will be made by the Coordinator EMBRC-ERIC in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet in the Grant Agreement. EMBRC- ERIC must pay due to the other beneficiaries within three months of receiving the funds. If not, it will have to justify itself to explain the reasons for the delay. As Coordinator, EMBRC- ERIC is not, under any circumstances, authorised to transfer funds to beneficiaries who have not yet joined the Consortium. There are three types of payments to beneficiaries:

- Pre-financing payment at the beginning of the action, i.e. 48.33% of the total amount indicated in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement;
- Interim payments to cover eligible costs incurred during the 3 reporting periods, i.e.
 - RP1 (01/12/22 - 31/05/24);
 - RP2 (01/06/24 - 30/11/25);
 - RP3 (01/12/25 - 30/11/26);
- Final payment after the end of the action.

They will be made in euro to the bank account indicated by the Coordinator and must be distributed without unjustified delay (restrictions may apply to distribution of the initial prefinancing payment; see Data Sheet, Point 4.2). Payments to this bank account will discharge the granting authority from its payment obligation.

- The cost of payment transfers will be borne as follows:
- The granting authority bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank;
- The beneficiary bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank;

The party causing a repetition of a transfer bears all costs of the repeated transfer. Payments by the granting authority will be considered to have been carried out on the date when they are debited to its account.

1. Pre-financing amount due

The aim of the pre-financing payment is to provide beneficiaries with a float (sufficient funds to cover the expenditure of beneficiary from the start of the project). It remains the property

The aim of the EU until the final payment. Pre-financing will not be paid before the Grant Agreement is signed by the beneficiaries. The pre-financing amount corresponds to 48.33% of the total amount indicated in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement.

Some of the conditions that must be fulfilled before the pre-financing payment include:

- Approval of project funding;
- Entry into force of the Grant Agreement;
- Receipt of dated, signed and stamped Financial Identifications.

For initial prefinancing (if any), the amount due, schedule and modalities are set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 4.2), which can be consulted in the Grant Agreement.

For additional prefinancing (if any), the amount due, schedule and modalities are also set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 4.2). However, if the statement on the use of the previous prefinancing payment shows that less than 70% was used, the amount set out in the Data Sheet will be reduced by the difference between the 70% threshold and the amount used.

The contribution to the Mutual Insurance Mechanism will be retained from the prefinancing payments (at the rate and in accordance with the modalities set out in the Data Sheet, see Point 4.2) and transferred to the Mechanism.

Prefinancing payments (or parts of them) may be offset (without the beneficiaries' consent) against amounts owed by a beneficiary to the granting authority — up to the amount due to that beneficiary.

For grants where the granting authority is the European Commission or an EU executive agency, offsetting may also be done against amounts owed to other Commission services or executive agencies.

Payments will not be made if the payment deadline or payments are suspended (see Articles 29 and 30).

For more detailed information, see the Art. 22.3.1 and 22.3.2 of the Grant Agreement.

2. Interim payment

Interim payments reimburse the eligible costs incurred for the implementation of the action during the corresponding reporting periods. The trigger for interim payment is the approval of the relevant periodic report (both financial and technical reports).

The total amount of pre-financing and interim payments will not exceed 85 percent of the maximum grant amount minus pre-financing and previous interim payments.

EMBRC-ERIC will pay to the beneficiary the amount due as interim payment within 30 days from receiving the periodic report except in the event of a suspension or termination. Before an interim payment is made, the following conditions must be satisfied:

- Approval of the periodic report (financial and technical report);
- Evidence that all specified conditions in the Grant Agreement have been met;

- The beneficiary has submitted a periodic report within 30 days following the end of each reporting period. The periodic report must include a periodic technical report and a periodic financial report.

For more detailed information, see the Art. 22.3.3 of the Grant Agreement.

3. Balance of payment

The payment of the balance reimburses the remaining part of the eligible costs incurred by the beneficiaries for the implementation of the action. Payment is subject to the approval of the final report. Its approval does not imply recognition of the compliance, authenticity, completeness or correctness of its content. The amount due as the balance is arrived at by the coordinator EMBRC-ERIC by deducting the total amount of pre-financing and interim payments (if any) already made, from the final grant amount.

Depending on the total amount of eligible costs incurred, the payment of balance can be in the form of recovery or payment:

- Recovery: if the total amount of earlier payments to the beneficiary is greater than the final grant amount the payment of the balance takes the form of a recovery. In such cases an invoice will be sent to the beneficiary;
- Payment: If the total amount of previous payments is less than the final amount of the grant, the payment conditions are fulfilled, the technical and financial reports are justified, EMBRC-ERIC, as coordinator, will make a payment after all payment conditions have been met.

In addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the coordinator must submit the final report within 60 days following the end of the last reporting period. The final report must include a final technical report and a final financial report.

4. Final payment

The final payment (payment of the balance) reimburses the remaining part of the eligible costs and contributions claimed for the implementation of the action (if any).

The final payment will be made in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 4.2).

Payment is subject to the approval of the final periodic report. Its approval does not imply recognition of compliance, authenticity, completeness or correctness of its content.

For more detailed information, see the Art. 22.3.1 of the Grant Agreement.

5. Suspension of payments

EMBRC-ERIC, as coordinator, may at any moment suspend, in whole or in part, the pre- financing payment and interim payments for one or more beneficiaries or the payment of the balance for all beneficiaries if a beneficiary has committed or is suspected of having committed substantial errors, irregularities, fraud or serious breach of obligations in the award procedure or under this Grant Agreement.

If the EMBRC-ERIC decides to suspend payment to a beneficiary, the beneficiary will receive a letter and a mail explaining the reasons for the suspension. The beneficiary is invited to present its explanations within 30 days of receiving the letter or email. If the actions are justified, the beneficiary will receive an e-mail and a letter notifying that the suspension procedure will not be pursued:

- If the actions are not considered justified by the EMBRC-ERIC coordinator or by the Project Adviser of the European Commission;

- If the actions are not considered justifiable by convincing documents and explanations;
- If no response has been submitted by mail or email, despite the recommendations of EMBRC-ERIC.

The beneficiary will receive a letter and e-mail of final suspension.

The suspension takes effect on the day the suspension confirmation letter and email are sent by EMBRC-ERIC. During the suspension, the periodic report(s) must not contain individual financial statements of the beneficiary concerned [and its related third parties].

If EMBRC-ERIC, with the agreement of the Project Adviser resumes payments, the beneficiary must have included them in the next periodic report.

6. Suspension of payment deadline

EMBRC-ERIC may at any moment suspend the payment deadline if a request for payment cannot be approved because:

- It does not comply with the provisions of the Grant Agreement;
- The technical reports or financial reports have not been submitted or are not complete or additional information is needed;
- There is doubt about the eligibility of the costs declared in the financial statements and additional checks, reviews, audits or investigations are necessary.

If EMBRC-ERIC decides to suspend the payment deadline for a beneficiary, a letter and a mail will be issued to the beneficiary concerned, specifying the reasons for suspension and informing the beneficiary concerned of a revised payment deadline.

7. Rejection of ineligible costs

EMBRC-ERIC will reject ineligible costs at the time of payment (interim or final payment) or even afterwards, in particular as a result of checks, reviews, audits or investigations. Ineligible costs will be rejected in their entirety, with the exception of flat-rate costs, which will be rejected in proportion to the tasks or parts of the action not implemented:

- If costs are rejected at the time of an interim or final payment, EMBRC-ERIC will calculate the interim or final payment after deducting these costs from the total eligible costs reported in the periodic or final summary financial statement;
- If costs are rejected after an interim payment but before the balance payment, and ineligible costs were reported in a periodic summary financial statement, EMBRC-ERIC will deduct those rejected costs from the total eligible costs reported in the next periodic summary financial statement;
- If any costs are rejected after the balance has been paid, EMBRC-ERIC will request a refund from the recipient by notifying them by email and mail.

The beneficiary will be notified by EMBRC-ERIC of all ineligible costs and will have the opportunity to respond to the notification within 30 days. If the beneficiary concerned does not respond to the notification or if its response is not valid as justification, EMBRC-ERIC in agreement with the Project Adviser, will deduct the sum of the ineligible costs from the total eligible costs.

8. Recoveries

Recoveries will be made, if — at beneficiary termination, final payment or afterwards — it turns out that the granting authority has paid too much and needs to recover the amounts undue.

Each beneficiary's financial responsibility in case of recovery is in principle limited to their own debt and undue amounts of their affiliated entities.

In case of enforced recoveries (see Article 22.4 from the Grant Agreement), affiliated entities will be held liable for repaying debts of their beneficiaries, if required by the granting authority (see Data Sheet, Point 4.4).

9. Enforced recovery

If payment is not made by the date specified in the debit note, the amount due will be recovered by:

- Offsetting the amount — without the coordinator or beneficiary's consent — against any amounts owed to the coordinator or beneficiary by the granting authority/ In exceptional circumstances, to safeguard the EU financial interests, the amount may be offset before the payment date specified in the debit note. For grants where the granting authority is the European Commission or an EU executive agency, debts may also be offset against amounts owed by other Commission services or executive agencies;
- Holding affiliated entities jointly and severally liable (if any, see Data Sheet, Point 4.4);
- Taking legal action (see Article 43 from the Grant Agreement) or, provided that the granting authority is the European Commission or an EU executive agency, by adopting an enforceable decision under Article 299 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) and Article 100(2) of EU Financial Regulation 2018/1046.

Note that financial guarantee and joint and several liability of beneficiaries are not applicable.

If the Mutual Insurance Mechanism was called on by the granting authority to intervene, recovery will be continued in the name of the Mutual Insurance Mechanism. If two debit notes were sent, the second one (in the name of the Mutual Insurance Mechanism) will be considered to replace the first one (in the name of the granting authority). Where the MIM intervened, offsetting, enforceable decisions or any other of the above-mentioned forms of enforced recovery may be used *mutatis mutandis*.

The amount to be recovered will be increased by late-payment interest at the rate set out in Article 22.5, Grant Agreement, from the day following the payment date in the debit note, up to and including the date the full payment is received.

Partial payments will be first credited against expenses, charges and late-payment interest and then against the principal.

Bank charges incurred in the recovery process will be borne by the beneficiary, unless Directive 2015/2366/17 applies.

For grants where the granting authority is an EU executive agency, enforced recovery by offsetting or enforceable decision will be done by the services of the European Commission (see also Article 43, Grant Agreement).

10. Consequences of non-compliance

The consequences are:

- If the granting authority does not pay within the payment deadlines (see above), the beneficiaries are entitled to late-payment interest at the rate applied by the European Central Bank (ECB) for its main refinancing operations in euros ('reference rate'), plus the rate specified in the Data Sheet (Point 4.2). The reference rate is the rate in force on the first day of the month in which the payment deadline expires, as published in the C series of the Official Journal of the European Union;

- If the late-payment interest is lower than or equal to EUR 200, it will be paid to the coordinator only on request submitted within two months of receiving the late payment. Late-payment interest is not due if all beneficiaries are EU Member States (including regional and local government authorities or other public bodies acting on behalf of a Member State for the purpose of this Agreement);
- If payments or the payment deadline are suspended (see Articles 29 and 30 from the Grant Agreement), payment will not be considered as late. Late-payment interest covers the period running from the day following the due date for payment (see above), up to and including the date of payment. Late-payment interest is not considered for the purposes of calculating the final grant amount;
- If the Coordinator breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 29 from the Grant Agreement) and the grant or the coordinator may be terminated (see Article 32 from the Grant Agreement). Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5.

G. Checks, audit, review and investigations

1. Checks, review and investigations

The Commission - during the implementation of the project or afterwards - checks, reviews, investigates, and audits the proper implementation of the project and its compliance with the grant agreement.

Where the granting authority is not the European Commission, the latter has the same rights of checks, reviews and audits as the granting authority.

The beneficiaries must — up to five years after the payment of the balance — keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declare as eligible. They must make them available upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits or investigations.

If there are on-going checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation or other pursuits of claims under the Grant Agreement, beneficiaries must keep the records and other supporting documentation until the end of these procedures. The beneficiaries must keep the original documents. Digital and digitalized documents are considered originals if they are authorized by the applicable national law.

2. Audit

The European Commission may — at any moment and up until 2 years after the payment of the balance — carry out an audit.

Audits normally concern mainly the financial implementation of the action by a beneficiary (i.e. financial and budgetary implementation), but may also cover technical aspects or compliance with other obligations under the sub-granting agreement. They consist in an in- depth examination (by professional (external or European Commission) auditors and according to the generally accepted audit standards) of the implementation of the action by the beneficiary. They may also extend to third parties involved in the action and third parties receiving financial support or a prize.

On the basis of the audit findings, a draft audit report will be drawn up.

The auditors will formally notify the draft audit report to the beneficiary concerned, which has 30 days from receiving notification to make observations (contradictory audit procedure).

The final audit report will take into account observations by the beneficiary concerned and will be formally notified to them.

Audits (including audit reports) will be in the language of the Agreement (English).

If the audit shows, ineligible costs, substantial errors, irregularities or fraud or serious breach of obligations, it may lead to suspension, termination, cost rejection, grant reduction and recovery and, in very serious cases, to exclusion and/or financial penalties.

7. Concluding remarks

As stated in Introduction, the Project Management Guide provides a guide to be used by all eDNAqua-Plan members to ensure an understanding of their roles and responsibilities in delivering the eDNAqua-Plan project through efficient and well managed processes. This document should be used by partners to complement the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Further guidelines may also be found on the EC portal.

If any item in this document is ambiguous, or if further assistance or advice is required, please contact the Project Manager: paulina.r.quevedo@embrc.eu

Appendix 1

Tasks and Task-leaders of the eDNAqua-Plan project

WP	Task	Title of the task	Lead (co-lead)	Contributors
1	1.1	Project Management	EMBRC	
	1.2	Communication & Dissemination	EMBRC	SSBE
	1.3	Stakeholder Engagement	SSBE	EMBRC
2	2.1	Inventory, overview and gap analysis of DNA barcoding initiatives and reference libraries	UMinho	IHU, UniLodz, SSBE, UDE, INRAE
	2.2	Inventory, overview and gap analysis of eDNA initiatives and repositories	EMBL-EBI	UniLodz, UNESCO, IHU
	2.3	Identification of workflows used currently for DNA-based biodiversity monitoring	SYKE	NIVA, UniLodz, UNESCO, IHU
3	3.1	Standards for genetic reference libraries	SU, INRAE	UMinho, UNESCO, EMBL-EBI
	3.2	Standards for eDNA data repositories	BIOPOLIS	SYKE, UNESCO, EMBL-EBI
	3.3	Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility	VLIZ, UVEG	UniLodz, UNESCO, EMBL-EBI
4	4.1	Testing eDNA library, workflows and infrastructure for marine monitoring using existing datasets	EVILVO	UNESCO, UMinho, UVEG, SYKE, WUR
	4.2	Testing eDNA library, workflow and infrastructure for freshwater monitoring using existing data sets	UDE	INRAE, SYKE, UVEG, BIOPOLIS
5	5.1	Blueprint for future system(s)/workflow(s)	VLIZ	UNESCO, EMBL-EBI, EMBRC, SSBE, LifeWatch, SYKE
	5.2	Roadmap for implementation	SSBE	UNESCO, EMBRC, VLIZ, LifeWatch?
	5.3	Business model and sustainability	LifeWatch	UDE, SYKE, SSBE, EMBRC

Appendix 2

Deliverables by due-month of the eDNAqua-Plan project

<i>WP</i>	<i>Deliverable No</i>	<i>Title of the deliverable</i>	<i>Lead beneficiary</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Dissemination level</i>	<i>Due month</i>
1	1.1	Project Management Guide	EMBRC-ERIC	Document, report	PU – Public	3
	1.2	Data Privacy and Data Management Plan	EMBRC-ERIC	Data Management Plan	PU – Public	4
	1.3	Communication and Dissemination Plan and Package	EMBRC-ERIC	Websites; patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	6
	1.4	eDNAqua-Plan Factsheet Template	EMBRC-ERIC	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU – Public	6
	1.5	eDNAqua-Plan Factsheet updates 1-3	SSBE	Demonstrator, pilot Prototype	PU – Public	36
	1.6	Data Management Plan	EMBRC-ERIC	Data Management Plan	PU – Public	36
	1.7	Communication and engagement Plan	EMBRC-ERIC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	36
	1.8	Data Management Plan update	EMBRC-ERIC	Data Management Plan	PU – Public	24
	2.1	Report on reference libraries	UMINHO	Document, report	PU – Public	12
2	2.2	Report on eDNA data repositories	EMBL	Document, report	PU – Public	12
	2.3	Report on eDNA data workflows	SYKE	Document, Report	PU – Public	12
3	3.1	Report on standards of reference databases	SU	Document, report	PU – Public	30
	3.2	Report on standards of eDNA repositories	EMBRC-ERIC	Document, report	PU – Public	30
	3.3	Report on interoperability	VLIZ	Document, report	PU – Public	30
4	4.1	Report on workflow pitfalls	EV ILVO	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU – Public	25
	4.2	Report with practical recommendations	UDE	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU – Public	30
5	5.1	Report describing the proposed optimal system(s)/workflow(s)	VLIZ	Document, report	PU – Public	30
	5.2	Vision FactSheet on a European eDNA digital ecosystem	SSBE	Document, report	PU – Public	35
	5.3	Roadmap for implementation of the optimal system(s)/workflow(s)	SSEB	Document, report	PU – Public	34

Appendix 3

Identified risks of the eDNAqua-Plan project

Risk: Failure to agree on search criteria and system for inventorying (WP2)

Likelihood: **Low**

Severity: **High**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: Dedicate sufficient time to discuss and set up a framework for the inventory.

Risk: Inaccessible data from some barcoding projects (WP2)

Likelihood: **Medium**

Severity: **Low / Medium**

Actively approach institutions and explain the purpose of this project.

Risk: Failure to agree on metadata requirements for valid reference records (WP3)

Likelihood: **Low**

Severity: **High**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: An overview of existing standards and practices will be used as a basis for conversation in a workshop promoting open dialogue between a broad range of stakeholders.

Risk: Model of mappings not found for metadata standards used in eDNA and other types of biodiversity repositories (WP3)

Likelihood: **Low**

Severity: **High**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: eDNAqua-Plan will capitalize on expertise available in the broad stakeholder community and partners data standardization to suggest the best solutions.

Risk: The proposed eDNA data ecosystem not technically feasible (WP3, WP4, WP5)

Likelihood: **Low**

Severity: **High**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: Collaboration between WP3, WP4 and WP5 will ensure that the needs of use cases, and the technical scope of the proposed data ecosystem solutions stay reasonable and remain practical for the stakeholder communities.

Risk: Use cases not sufficiently documented to properly evaluate the eDNA data ecosystem (WP3, WP4)

Likelihood: **Low**

Severity: **Medium**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: Various use cases have been selected from different partners experienced with the collection of eDNA datasets, thereby reducing the likelihood that all selected datasets would be insufficiently documented.

Risk: eDNA data of the citizen science use case not available in time (WP4)

Likelihood: **Low**

Severity: **High**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: Evaluation of flows in documenting eDNA data collection when not collected by scientists is of most relevance here.

Risk: Failure to agree on search criteria and system for inventorying (WP2)

Likelihood: **Medium**

Severity: **Low**

Proposed risk-mitigation measures: Evaluation of flows in documenting eDNA data collection when not collected by scientists is of most relevance here, therefore even without the eDNA sequence data this citizen science project will provide valuable information for WP3 and WP5.

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